

**INTERLAMINAR SHEAR MODULI OF GRAPHITE/EPOXY
CROSS-PLY LAMINATE**

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ABSTRACT

A whole-field micromechanical deformation analysis was performed on a thick $[90_2/0]_n$ graphite-epoxy laminate. Rail-shear loading conditions were used and deformations were measured by high-sensitivity moire interferometry. Shear strains were determined in individual plies and in the resin-rich zones between plies. Effective interlaminar moduli are given for design purposes.

INTRODUCTION

This work examined the deformation of a thick cross-ply laminate in interlaminar shear. Twin objectives were (1) an in-depth study of the phenomenological behavior of a specific composite laminate in shear and (2) the determination of the elastic interlaminar shear moduli G_0 and G_{90} for the individual 0 deg and 90 deg plies, respectively, and the effective interlaminar shear modulus of the laminate.

Rail-shear loading conditions were used [1], selected because of the limited thickness of the laminate. Moire interferometry [2] was applied for deformation measurements. This appears to be the only method capable of measuring shear deformations of individual plies in a laminate. Adams and Walrath measured average values of interlaminar shear moduli using the Iosipescu specimen geometry and electrical strain gages that spanned numerous plies [3]. ASTM round-robin measurements of in-plane shear moduli using rail-shear configurations exhibited a high degree of scatter [4], but interlaminar shear properties were not addressed. The present experimental study appears to be unique and definitive.

EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

The specimens were loaded in interlaminar shear as illustrated in Fig.1. Specimen was subjected to a stress concentration by direct compressive loading at the corners.

Whole-field contour maps of in-plane displacements U and V were obtained by moire interferometry [2]. This is an optical method using coherent light and featuring subwavelength sensitivity and high spatial resolution. It is capable of measuring deformations in composites on the ply level.

The principle of moire interferometry is depicted schematically in Fig.2, together with relevant fringe order-displacement-strain equations. In this method a crossed-line diffraction grating is replicated on the specimen and it deforms together with the loaded specimen. A virtual reference grating created by interference of two coherent beams B_1 and B_2 is superimposed on the specimen

grating. The specimen and reference gratings form a fringe pattern which is a contour map of the in-plane specimen displacement.

DEFORMATION FIELDS AND QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS

Figure 3 is fringe patterns depicting the U and V displacement fields for specimen. The V fields show larger shear deformations in the 90 deg plies (by virtue of more closely spaced fringes), compared to the 0 deg plies. Rigid body rotations occurred at the ends of the specimens, revealed by fringes of rotation evident in both the U and V fields. The shear strains in the specimen are much larger than the normal strains.

The extraction of detailed micromechanical behavior is greatly simplified by the use of carrier fringes [5]. The carrier fringes can be introduced by an adjustment of beam B_1 or B_2 in Fig.2. Carrier fringes transform the appearance of the load-induced fringes by adding (or subtracting) a uniform fringe gradient across the field. Figure 4 is an enlarged view showing the central portion of the V field for specimen 1, after a carrier of extension was applied, i.e., carrier fringes perpendicular to the y axis. Now, the fringes exhibit essentially constant slopes across the 0 deg plies, essentially constant but greater slopes across the 90 deg plies, and even greater slopes in resin-rich zones between 0 deg and 90 deg plies. It can be shown [5] that these slopes are proportional to the dominant term, N_y/X , in the shear strain relationship given in Fig.2. Although these gradients could not be recognized in Fig.3, the distribution of N_y/X can be extracted with high fidelity when carrier fringes are employed. The companion term, N_x/y , is readily determined from the U field of Fig.3.

Figure 5 represents the same V field, but carrier fringes of rotation were applied in this case. These add a uniform gradient throughout the field, one that opposes and nearly cancels the load-induced N_y/X in the specimen [5]. The carrier fringes are very nearly vertical and they do not alter the gradient N_y/y . Consequently, this term is easily measured from Fig.5, to allow easy determination of N_y/y by the relationship given in Fig.2.

QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS

1. Shear Strains

The distribution of shear strains along the length of the specimen is shown in Fig.6. For the V field, data were taken from patterns containing carrier fringes (as in Fig.6) and the cross-derivative term was calculated from measured fringe slopes. For the U field, the cross-derivative term was calculated from gradients measured on Figs. 4. The γ_{xy} distributions were determined along individual 0 deg and 90 deg plies located within the central third of the width of the specimen.

Figure 7 is a graph of the shear strain along the horizontal centerline of the specimen. The insert is a photograph of the central portion of the specimen, showing the ply sequence; darker zones are 90 deg plies and lighter zones are 0 deg plies. Shear strains are generally smallest in 0 deg plies; they are generally larger in 90 deg plies; and they are largest in resin-rich zones between plies.

A dramatic feature of this graph is the variation of strain levels in nominally equivalent plies. The shear strains in 0 deg plies, measured at the horizontal centerline, was averaged to obtain $[\gamma_C^{av}]_0$, where C denotes the horizontal centerline. This average value was

$$(\gamma_C^{av})_0 = 3.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$$

For the 90 deg plies, the average was

$$(\gamma_C^{av})_{90} = 5.0 \cdot 10^{-3}$$

The resin-rich zones between plies exhibit strains of about $8 \cdot 10^{-3}$. In each case, the variations appear to be randomly distributed about the average values.

Returning to Fig.6, it should be noted that the plies chosen for analysis were not selected arbitrarily. Instead, the data for Fig.6 were taken from 0 deg ply no. 5 and the neighboring 90 deg ply on the left side (noted by arrows in Fig.9). These were selected because the shear strains they exhibited were nearly the same as the average of corresponding plies, $(\gamma_C^{av})_{0,90}$. These plies were considered to be most representative.

2. Interlaminar Shear Moduli of Individual Plies

Shear moduli were calculated on the basis of two specific propositions:

Proposition 1. The shear modulus G is constant within any single ply. This proposition provides that shear stress is proportional to shear strain at every point in the ply and therefore their average values are in the same proportion, or

$$G_a = \frac{\tau^{av}}{(\gamma_L^{av})_a} \quad (1)$$

where subscript a designates a specific ply τ^{av} is the average shear stress on the ply (i.e., P/LT as defined in Fig.2).

In conflict with this proposition, the observed random variations of shear strains along the length of a ply are accepted as real effects. These variations must be caused largely by variations of the shear modulus within the ply.

Proposition 2. The shear modulus of any ply is inversely proportional to the shear strain at the horizontal centerline. This prescribes that the shear strain at the horizontal centerline is representative for the ply, i.e., it is not an anomalous value. It leads to the relationship

$$\frac{G_b}{G_a} = \frac{(\gamma_C)_a}{(\gamma_C)_b} \quad \text{or} \quad G_b = \frac{(\gamma_C)_a}{(\gamma_C)_b} \frac{\tau^{av}}{(\gamma_L^{av})_a}$$

where subscript b designates any other ply of the same fiber orientation and is the shear strain measured at the horizontal centerline. To obtain the representative value of G for all 0 deg plies (or 90 deg plies), $(\gamma_C)_b$ is taken as the average value $(\gamma_C^{av})_0$ (or $(\gamma_C^{av})_{90}$). Then

$$G_{0,90} = \frac{(\gamma_C)_a}{(\gamma_C^{av})_{0,90}} \frac{\tau^{av}}{(\gamma_L^{av})_a} \quad (2)$$

The shear moduli of 0 deg and 90 deg plies were calculated by Eq. (2), using values of γ_L^{av} from Fig.6 and γ_C^{av} from Fig.7.

3. Interlaminar Shear Modulus of the Laminate

The effective interlaminar shear modulus of the laminate, G^{eff} , is the value that would predict the same macroscopic deformation of the laminate as would a ply-by-ply analysis. It is an integrated or smeared property that averages the performance of individual plies. The subscript n represents the number of repeated ply sequences in the specimen.

G^{eff} can be determined from these tests by

$$G_{[90_2/0]_n}^{eff} = \frac{\tau^{av}}{\gamma_{W,L}^{av}} \quad (3)$$

where $\gamma_{W,L}^{av}$ is the shear strain averaged along the width and length of the specimen. The averaging can be done in two steps. Firstly, the shear strain averaged across the width of the specimen at the horizontal centerline is given by

$$\gamma_W^{av} = \frac{\Delta N y}{f W}$$

where N is the change of fringe order at the horizontal centerline across the specimen width, w , and f is the frequency of the reference grating (2400 lines/mm). Secondly, the averaging factors that account for variations along the specimen length are taken from Fig.6. as γ_L^{av}/γ_C . Since this factor might be different for 0 deg and 90 deg plies, it is proportioned according to the relative number of these plies, such that

$$\gamma_{W,L}^{av} = \frac{\Delta N y}{f W} \left[\frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{\gamma_L^{av}}{\gamma_C} \right)_0 + \frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{\gamma_L^{av}}{\gamma_C} \right)_{90} \right]$$

4. Rule of Mixtures, $G_{0,90}^{eff}$

If the influence of resin-rich zones is neglected, the shear modulus of the laminate could be calculated by the rule of mixtures as

$$G_{[90_2/0]_n}^{eff} = \frac{1}{3} G_0 + \frac{2}{3} G_{90} \quad (5)$$

The results are given in Table I. Compared to the rule-of-mixtures values of $G_{[90_2/0]_n}^{eff}$, the effective values determined by measurements (which do include the effect of the resin-rich zone) are lower by factors $k=0.864$ for specimen. Factor k is the ratio of the effective shear modulus of the laminate as determined by measurements to that determined by the rule of mixtures.

5. EFFECTIVE MODULI OF INDIVIDUAL PLYS

Effective values of the interlaminar shear modulus for individual plies can be defined that account for the influence of resin-rich zones in real laminates. We suggest the relationship

$$G_{0,90}^{eff} = K G_{0,90} \quad (6)$$

where k (defined above) is a correction factor that accounts for the compliant resin-rich portion of the ply.

CONCLUSIONS

This micromechanical analysis of shear deformations documents the detailed response of a real composite laminate. The behavior of individual plies and the separate behavior in the interface region between plies have been observed quantitatively and qualitatively. The results offer phenomenological knowledge of material response and enhance insight and understanding. They also permit the determination of interlaminar shear properties for engineering design.

The specimen material exhibited a characteristic of real laminates: the resin distribution was not uniform. Instead, the resin concentration was greater near the ply interfaces than at the center of the plies.

In design practice, the integrated values should be used. Accordingly, we recommend design values for individual plies of this material and for the laminate as

$$G_0^{\text{eff}} = 3.2 \text{ GPa} = 470,000 \text{ psi}$$

$$G_{90}^{\text{eff}} = 2.4 \text{ GPa} = 350,000 \text{ psi}$$

$$C_{[90_2/0]_n}^{\text{eff}} = 2.7 \text{ GPa} = 390,000 \text{ psi}$$

REFERENCES

- [1] J.M. Whitney, D. L. Stansbarger, H. B. Howell: "Analysis of the Rail Shear Test—Applications and Limitations", J. Composite Materials, pp. 24-34, (Jan. 1971)
- [2] D. Post, "Moire Interferometry", Chap. 7, Handbook of Experimental Mechanics, A. S. Kobayashi, Ed., Prentice Hall, Englewood Cliffs, NJ (1987).
- [3] D. F. Adams and D. E. Walrath, "In-plane and Interlaminar Iosipescu Shear Properties of Various Graphite/Epoxy Laminates", J. Composites Technology & Research, 9(3), pp. 88-94 (Fall 1987).
- [4] P. A. Lockwood, "Results of the ASTM Round-Robin on the Rail Shear Test of Composites", Composites Technology Review, 3(2), pp. 83-86 (Summer 1981).
- [5] Y. Guo, D. Post and R. Czarnek, "The Magic of Carrier Fringes in Moire Interferometry", Experimental Mechanics (to be published).
- [6] C. T. Herakovich, H. W. Bergner and D. E. Bowles, "A Comparative Study of Composite Shear Specimens Using the Finite-Element Method", Test Methods and Design Allowables for Fibrous Composites, ASTM STP 734, C.C. Chamis, Ed., ASTM, pp. 129-151 (1981).

Fig.1. Shear specimen was cut from a 200 mm (8 in.) diameter laminated composite tube.

Fig.2. Moire interferometry and relevant equations. $f = 2400$ lines/mm. sensitivity = $0.417 \mu\text{m}/\text{fringe order}$.

Fig.3. N_x and N_y fringe patterns, depicting the U and V fields, respectively. Specimen I. $P = 3.18$ kN (714 1b).

Fig.4. N_y pattern with carrier fringes of extension, for central portion of N_y field of Fig.3. The insert at the bottom is a photograph showing the ply sequence.

Fig.5. N_y pattern with carrier fringes of rotation, for central portion of N_y field of Fig.4.

Fig. 6. Shear strains along individual plies

Fig. 7. Interlaminar shear strains along the width of the specimen, at the center of its length. The insert is a photograph of the plies.

2. Stress Analysis and Buckling Analysis

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